

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

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*Elektron nashr. 1086 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-noyabrda ruxsat etildi.*

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Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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AGRICULTURE COOPERATIVE MODELS

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Abstract: This study explores agricultural cooperative models by analyzing governance structures, operational challenges, and financial performance. Primary data was collected through interviews and surveys with cooperative members, while secondary data came from academic and industry sources. The findings contribute to understanding the effectiveness and sustainability of cooperative models.

Key words: farmers, agriculture sector, agricultural cooperatives.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot qishloq xo'jaligi kooperativlari modellari, boshqaruv tuzilmalari, operatsion muammolar va moliyaviy samaradorlikni o'rganishga qaratilgan. Asosiy ma'lumotlar kooperativ a'zolari bilan o'tkazilgan intervyular va so'rovnomalardan orqali yig'ilgan, ikkilamchi ma'lumotlar esa ilmiy va tarmoq manbalaridan olingan. Natijalar kooperativ modellarning samaradorligi va barqarorligini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: fermerlar, qishloq xo'jaligi sektori, qishloq xo'jaligi kooperativlari.

Аннотация: В исследовании рассматриваются модели сельскохозяйственных кооперативов, их структуры управления, операционные вызовы и финансовая эффективность. Первичные данные собраны через опросы и интервью с членами кооперативов, а вторичные – из научных и отраслевых источников. Результаты способствуют пониманию эффективности и устойчивости кооперативных моделей.

Ключевые слова: фермеры, аграрный сектор, сельскохозяйственные кооперативы.

INTRODUCTION

In the agriculture sector, cooperatives are important in both developed and developing countries. Historically, independent farmers have been able to resist the market dominance wielded by regional and international retailers by using cooperatives as their primary institutional and organizational tool. By enabling producers to combine most or all of the marketing and processing procedures into one or a small number of phases, they also help to shorten the supply chain and enable significant savings on transaction and other intermediation expenses. The agricultural sector accounts for 23.7 % of total Uzbekistan manufacturing output, 426,3 trillion sum worth of production.

The research traces the sector-specific organizational features of agricultural production to the economic nature of agricultural cooperatives. Although those characteristics have been used to support the superiority of family-based organizations in agriculture thus far, this paper argues that they also offer a way to explain the emergence of transaction costs and market power imbalances that give agricultural cooperatives a functional niche. This will lead to an explanation of why cooperatives are dramatically important in agriculture, particularly in the institutional context of Asian countries where family farming is a dominant form of agricultural organization. Nonetheless, this institutional background emphasizes the significant challenges that agricultural cooperatives must overcome. It will be demonstrated that agricultural cooperatives are subject to continual strain due to the increased duties that the institutional structure of modern Asian agri-food systems imposes on them.

Traditional explanations of the significance of family farms have focused on the high emphasis that family farms place on land ownership and independent production, as well as the impossibility of a hierarchical agricultural production structure due to monitoring and supervisory issues. These theories tend to minimize the fact that family farms' transaction cost-saving benefits come at a cost: they are less able to effectively reach big sizes. These disadvantages represent the major motives for the creation of agricultural cooperatives, whose role lies in enabling the realization of advantages of hierarchical organization in agriculture while avoiding the need to incur its transaction costs, which are prohibitively high in this sector, and without forcing family farms out of independent production. Since it only applies to the agricultural industry, this explanation of agricultural cooperatives is sector-specific.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Agricultural cooperatives have been extensively studied for their role in enhancing farm sustainability and economic viability. Candemir, Duvaleix, and Latruffe provide a comprehensive literature review highlighting how cooperatives influence various dimensions of farm sustainability, including economic, social, and environmental aspects. Fathinia et al. delve into the historical development and benefits of agricultural cooperatives,

emphasizing their capacity to foster resilient and sustainable food systems through cooperation, adaptation, and innovation.

Pliakoura, Beligiannis, and Kontogeorgos identify significant barriers to adopting the agricultural cooperative model of entrepreneurship. Their systematic literature review categorizes these barriers, providing insights into challenges that cooperatives face in various contexts. Bekolli, Guardiola, and Meca explore profit allocation in agricultural supply chains, focusing on the nexus of cooperation and compensation. Their research employs cooperative game theory to analyze how agents coordinate actions to maximize profits within agricultural cooperatives.

Galor’s work on cooperative principles underscores the importance of member ownership and the goal of operating at cost to serve members optimally. His studies on the demutualization of cooperatives, such as Tnuva in Israel, provide valuable insights into the challenges and dynamics of cooperative structures.

These studies collectively offer a nuanced understanding of agricultural cooperative models, their benefits, challenges, and the factors influencing their sustainability and effectiveness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized primary data from structured interviews and surveys with cooperative members and managers, offering qualitative insights into governance and challenges. Secondary data from academic journals and reports provided broader trends. Data analysis combined qualitative methods to identify themes and quantitative techniques, such as statistical analysis, to evaluate cooperative performance and efficiency.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Agricultural cooperatives in the Asian hemisphere are now facing an especially challenging and unfriendly business climate. The major challenges faced by cooperatives since then include fierce competition with powerful food and agricultural input conglomerates as well as financing shortages caused by deteriorating capital markets. These challenges laid bare a number of internal constraints that have become known as the property rights problems (also known as incentive problems) of agricultural cooperatives (Cook 1995). These issues prevented agricultural cooperative members from making effective group decisions and deterred them from investing large amounts of risk capital (Cook and Iliopoulos 2000). Numerous cooperative conversions into investor-oriented businesses, liquidations, and experiments with new cooperative forms were the outcomes of these issues (Cross et al. 2009; Chaddad and Cook 2004). These models were arranged by Chaddad and Cook (2004) into a continuum that was bounded on one side by the investor-oriented firm and on the other by the conventional cooperative. The authors contend that the definition and allocation of ownership rights to the firm’s principal stakeholders separate cooperative arrangements. They distinguish five nontraditional cooperative models between the extremes of the traditional agricultural cooperative and the investor-oriented firm: investorshare cooperatives, member investor cooperatives, new generation cooperatives, proportional investment cooperatives, and cooperatives with capital-seeking entities.

Table 1. Property rights problems of agricultural cooperatives.

Problems	Description
Free Rider Problem	A situation where current members or non-members use a resource for their individual benefit, and property rights are not well suited nor enforced in a way that ensures that current member-patrons or current non-member-patrons bear the full costs of their actions and/or receive the full benefits they generate. This situation is typical for open membership cooperatives.
Horizon Problem	A situation where a member’s residual claim on the net income generated by an asset is shorter than the productive life of that asset (Porter and Scully, 1988). This problem is caused by restrictions on transferability of residual claimant rights and the restricted liquidity through a secondary market for the transfer of such rights. The horizon problem creates an investment environment in which there is a disincentive for members to contribute to growth opportunities. This problem is particularly severe with respect to investment in research and development, advertisement and other intangible assets.

Portfolio Problem	A situation where cooperative members, due to the lack of transferability, liquidity, and appreciation mechanisms for the exchange of residual claims, are not able to adjust their cooperative asset portfolio to match their personal risk preferences. In cooperatives, the investment decision is “tied” to the patronage decision and thus, from an investment point of view, members hold suboptimal portfolios. As a result, members attempt to encourage cooperative decision-makers to rearrange the cooperative’s investment portfolio even if the reduced risk means lower expected returns.
Control Problem	A situation of divergence of interests between the membership and their representative board of directors (principal) and management (agent). Since the information provided and external pressures exerted by publicly traded equity instruments (stock market) is not present in cooperatives, and the members serving on the Board of Directors may have little or no experience in effectively exercising control, governance bodies operate with a handicap.
Influence Costs Problem	A situation where members attempt to influence collective decision-making to their own advantage. As shares in most cooperatives are neither transferable nor tradable, members that cannot exit the cooperative are left with only the voice option (Hirschman, 1970). Especially if the cooperative is engaged in a wide range of activities, influence activities complicate collective decision-making, and lead to wrong decisions or no decisions at all.

The primary issues with conventional cooperative property rights, which are typified by open membership and non-transferability of claims on the organization’s assets, are enumerated and explained in Table 1. Traditional cooperatives are defined by either reinvesting net residual into locked assets (mostly in Asian countries) or by having members’ nontransferable and redeemable capital shares. These characteristics of the conventional cooperative property rights structure lead to a number of incentive issues, which are detailed in Table 1.

The use of common resources in conjunction with democratic membership rights leads to and encourages either the opportunistic reduction of work effort (Williamson 1973) or the overuse of common assets, as in the tragedy of the commons problem (Hardin 1960; Ostrom 1990; Tortia 2011). This is the root cause of free riding. The portfolio problem is related to the inability to differentiate investments in the presence of common or socialized assets, whereas the horizon problem is related to the limited temporal horizon of permanence of the cooperative’s members in the presence of asset indivisibilities (Furubotn and Pejovich 1970). Finally, the conflicting interests and desires inside a democratically run organization, as well as the associated costs of ownership, are the root causes of the control problem and the influence cost problem.

The basic plan was altered in a variety of ways by new cooperative models, which is typically seen to lead to inefficiencies in investment and group decision-making. Two primary categories of altered property rights are identified (see Chaddad and Cook 2004). The first group includes proportional investment cooperatives, member-investor cooperatives and new generation cooperatives. In these cases, ownership rights are restricted to member-patrons. The second group includes cooperatives with capital seeking entities and investor share cooperatives. In the first group, proportional investment cooperatives differ from the more traditional model only because members are required to acquire an amount of capital proportional to their patronage shares.

To convert internally generated money to patronage shares, capital management rules are necessary. Net surpluses in member investor cooperatives are allocated based on capital holdings rather than patronage, however a combination of the two may be developed. Distributions may be made in the form of dividends or through the increase in value of current stock.

The two methods listed above are the most conventional changes to cooperative property rights, and they have been tried for many years in the majority of nations. The 1970s and 1980s saw the emergence of new generation cooperatives in the US (Harris et al. 1996). Because they link equity to delivery rights, they are seen as a novel form of modification of cooperative property rights. New generation cooperatives are closed membership organizations where delivery rights are interchangeable but the overall number of members is often constant. In addition, member-patrons are required to acquire delivery rights on the basis of expected patronage. Given these basic rules, a secondary market for delivery rights can be created where such rights can also be sold to new members, upon approval by the cooperative. Complicated marketing contracts that also incorporate assessments of product quality govern the actual product delivery. Cooperatives of the new generation provide the potential for valuable and marketable shares. Members can sell their delivery rights on the secondary market, which reduces the requirement for members’ shares to be redeemable and

the resulting volatility of the business capital. New generation cooperatives' property structures include an incentive alignment mechanism that might result in significant financial rewards for acquiring the company's stock. However, members' willingness to pay the upfront price of their delivery rights in terms of the firm equity presupposes that the market for delivery rights works smoothly enough, because otherwise incoming members can incur substantial losses given the non-redeemability of their equity shares. Finally, the perfect identification of member-patrons with the organization's owners is overcome by new cooperative models in the second category. In the case of cooperatives with capital-seeking businesses, outside ownership is permitted through partnerships or the establishment of controlled subsidiaries; in the case of investor share cooperatives, it is permitted through direct involvement of external investors in the company equity. This final approach reduces residual rights while increasing the opportunity to purchase equity capital on financial markets.

It should be noted that Chaddad and Cook's (2004) continuum does not provide a clear method of connecting the particular property rights issues to a particular cooperative model. To solve more than one of the five property rights issues, different organizational innovations are included into each cooperative model. These innovations aim to both ease collective decision-making and give cooperative members compelling incentives to contribute risk capital to their cooperative. However, it can be seen that the first three property rights issues support the first objective, while the other two clarify the second.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Cooperatives are therefore facing pressure to embrace new governance models that are more and more like to those of investor-owned businesses. Cooperatives have responded to both internal and external challenges by implementing new property rights models that aim to maintain the fundamental governance structure of cooperatives, which links farmer-members with the controlling patron, improve the ability to raise capital—most importantly, equity—and simultaneously strengthen the power of economic incentives. This argument's main policy implication is that policymakers must understand the conflicts that exist between agricultural cooperatives' institutional embeddedness and economic nature. The economic nature of agricultural cooperatives is reflected in policy tools such as providing tax exemptions, attractive loan conditions, technical aid, and limited protection from antitrust laws. Cooperatives' limited scope and propensity to forgo dimensional expansions that are solely used to boost market shares and market power give them immunity from antitrust laws. However, in many nations, such as Italy, tax exemptions or tax benefits are justified by the cooperatives' non-profit status, as well as by their full or partial socialization and indivisibility. However, ensuring that policymakers understand the need for new unconventional cooperation models and for modifying legislative frameworks to conform to these new models is the fundamental public policy dilemma. This paper has demonstrated that the purpose of these models is to align the self-provisioning core of agricultural cooperatives with the requirements of the embedded institutional structure, rather than to attempt to violate antitrust laws.

For example, the closed membership policy of new generation cooperatives may represent not an attempt to increase profits by controlling supply, but rather a tool for operating the cooperative's processing plant at optimal capacity, thus overcoming some of the most serious challenges represented by free-riding, the horizon problem, and the portfolio problem.

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Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

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Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 11

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

